
STAGES OF FACULTY DEVELOPMENT FOR HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS OF UKRAINE'S SECURITY AND DEFENSE SECTOR

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Abstract

This article outlines the specifics of managing the development of professional competence of scientific-pedagogical employees of the higher education institution of the security and defence sector of Ukraine following modern trends in pedagogy and training of employees in formal and informal education. This article considers the sequence of faculty professional competence development and the stages of this process in the higher education institutions of Ukraine's security and defence sector as modern. Also, practical tools for managing this process in the context of its implementation in practice are identified.

Key words: faculty staff, professional competence development, higher education institution, the security and defence sector, informal education, management.

Introduction

The large-scale armed aggression of the Russian Federation against Ukraine became a catalyst for changes in all spheres of the security and defence sector of the state. Of course, military education was not left out of this process because, in the current conditions, the state's demand for improving the quality of military personnel education is growing. The war drew attention to the critical need to assess the effectiveness of training military personnel and rethink approaches to their training. At the same time, in connection with the strengthening of cooperation with NATO and the desire of our country to integrate with the European Union, military education faces the task of adaptation to European standards, norms and practices. Additional difficulties arise in connection with the transition of the Armed Forces of Ukraine to NATO standards. This involves modernising weapons and equipment and reviewing approaches to military education at all levels. First, this requires an in-depth analysis of European pedagogical methods, organisational principles, and practical military training experience. In the context of the implementation of NATO standards and procedures in the security and defence sector of Ukraine, the concept of transformation of the military education system was developed, which defines the tasks of applying new approaches to the formation of the structure and content of the military education system, improving its quality [1].

The quality criteria of higher education include, among others, the provision of the educational process by qualified faculty staff. Much attention is paid to the issues of professional competence and its faculty development for higher education institutions (HEIs), in particular the military ones: licensing conditions for conducting educational activities have been introduced [2], a professional standard has been approved for the group of professions "Faculty staff of higher education institutions" [3], requirements have been defined to advance the faculty qualification [4]. In addition, faculty training for HEIs takes place within the framework of implementing the NATO DEEP-Ukraine (Defence Education Enhancement Program) program to build the institutional

capacity of higher military educational institutions and the comprehensive package of NATO assistance to Ukraine [5].

Today, the improvement of the faculty's professional competence usually takes place in formal and informal education. It should be noted that in the faculty staff professional development, the potential of developing professional competence at work [6] as one of the forms of informal education remains underestimated. The practicality and necessity of research into the management of the faculty professional competence development processes for the HEIs of the security and defence sector determine the article's relevance.

Theoretical background

The analysis of the latest research and publications. As a result of the study of theoretical developments and modern research, it was determined that the management of the faculty professional competence development is a pedagogically and socially significant problem, the theoretical basis of which is: the theory of pedagogical management (V. Bondar, Yu. Konarzhevskiy, V. Maslov, P. Tretyakov); the concept of educational monitoring (H. Yelnikova, O. Lokshina, A. Mayorov, D. Fishman), psychological and pedagogical foundations of creative personality development in the conditions of continuous professional education (I. Beh, N. Bibik, N. Burynska, I. Zyazyun, N. Kolomynskiy, V. Madzigon, S. Maksimenko, V. Oliynyk, O. Pehota). Such scientists as V. Yagupov, V. Osyodlo, A. Vitchenko, V. Vergun, S. Gladun, and I. Palagniuk studied the problems of the professionalism of faculty staff and the quality of education in the military sphere. O. Zlobina covered in her research the practical training of military personnel within the framework of the DEEP program for improving military education. N. Vavilova, O. Mityagin, and N. Shabatina considered the issue of ensuring the quality of military education in NATO member countries and Ukraine.

Investigating the problems of military education management, M. Neshchadym and S. Poltorak single out the issue of training "military teachers of the new formation" [7, p. 312]. At the same time, these scientists leave for consideration the problem of managing the faculty staff's professional competence development for HEIs of the security and defence sector.

Among the most relevant foreign studies in education for adults, models of the educational cycle and teacher training, the works of D. Kolb, D. Kirkpatrick, D. Hoffmann, and H. Dreyfus should be noted. Modern trends in the development of human capital, in particular in the field of higher education in the leading countries of the world, among which the development of professionals in the process of performing their functional duties (learning at work) are the subject of scientific research by A. Furnham, J. Taylor, P. Simons, D. McGregor, A. Beaumont, E. Mayo and many others researched the personnel management.

Based on the analysis of the scientific literature, we can state that Ukraine and the world have accumulated considerable experience in organising the faculty staff professional training. At the same time, it was established that the issue of managing the development of faculty staff professional competence of HEIs of the security and defence sector has not been sufficiently researched, identified and systematised.

Purpose. To determine the sequence and stages of the faculty staff professional competence development, to highlight modern and practical tools for managing this process in the context of its implementation in higher education institutions of the security and defence sector. To determine the sequence and stages of the faculty staff professional competence development, to highlight modern and practical tools for managing this process in the context of its implementation in HEIs of the security and defence sector.

Result and Discussion

Modern trends in the development of professional competencies of specialists are based on the concept of lifelong education, the essence of which boils down to the continuity of this process regardless of profession, age, work experience, position, etc. The rapid development of information technologies, the need for employees to possess an increasingly broad set of soft skills (such as creativity, critical and analytical thinking, complex problem solving, and cognitive flexibility), new life challenges, the emergence of new professions – all this leads to the need for constant development of higher education institutions and the growth of requirements for the faculty staff level of competence. An urgent issue of military special pedagogy at the current stage is the search for ways to overcome contradictions in pedagogical management. This is evidenced by the insufficient level of faculty staff of military HEIs training for teaching in educational programs following the NATO standards, as well as the use of outdated approaches and principles during the formation of the structure and content of military education, the imperfect process of forecasting its development [8].

For many years, Ukraine's military pedagogy did not rely on innovative educational programs for non-military personnel but their specialised education. It was certainly professional, but not a profession in the full sense of the word – rather, a semi-professional kind, similar to the medieval craft guilds, where the secrets of mastery were passed from master to novices in the profession through a process of initiation into a specific area of professional knowledge and skills. In this sense, military pedagogy was incapable of development but only of reproduction: professional knowledge remained static, and the educational process was cyclical. These observations are supported by the conclusions of experts of the NATO DEEP-Ukraine program [5], in which, in particular, the requirement for professionalisation of the military educational community is specified.

The problem of the effectiveness of pedagogical management in military special education can be solved only by ensuring the high professional competence of each faculty member. To achieve this, we would like to draw attention to the fact that the faculty staff positions in the majority of Ukraine's HEIs, and HEIs of the security and defence sector are no exception, are held by persons who meet the requirements of regulatory and legal acts. Among the list of criteria, there are no requirements for the developed professional pedagogical competence, but only the experience of serving in the positions of scientific fellows or faculty members [9], which can be replaced by the experience of military service in the commanding and HQ officers' positions. It would be logical to assume that the HEI should take care of the development of the professional competence of persons appointed to the faculty staff positions. To acquire the ability to perform the tasks of management of military special education in the HEIs of the security and defence sector, we propose to improve the system of the faculty staff professional competence development and consider it at the following stages, which, according to the chronology can be defined as follows (figure 1):

- 1) the initial stage (orientation and adaptation to the position of the faculty staff);
- 2) developmental stage (development of professional competence at work under the guidance of mentors, self-development);
- 3) in-depth stage (obtaining the scientific degree of Ph.D. in Education).

At the initial stage, it is essential to focus on acquiring a basic level of professional competence development. In addition to studying the requirements of the governing documents, which regulate the specifics of the organisation of the educational process in the HEIs of the security and defence sector, novice faculty members must complete a course of pedagogical mastery. After all, fulfilling all the requirements stipulated by normative legal acts, orders, and decisions is not enough for a person appointed to the faculty staff position to become an educator. Such a course lasting 1–2 weeks should include the following topics: educational cycle; peculiarities of perception

on memorising information; the basics of modern learning theory (experiential learning, active learning, learning styles), stages of an educational session, drawing up a lesson plan; visualisation tools and their creation; the role of the faculty member in the educational session; modern views on the educator's interaction with the students; favourable educational environment and means of its creation, evaluation of learning results. It is crucial that, at this stage, novice teachers have a scientific and theoretical basis for their pedagogical activity, separate general and professional competence, defined by the professional standard for the group of professionals "Faculty staff of higher education institutions" [3].

Figure 1. Stages of the faculty staff professional competence development in the higher educational institutions of the security and defence sector of Ukraine

At the development stage, the principle of "education during a military career" is fully implemented, and conditions are created to form a new style of military leadership among the faculty and staff of higher education institutions in the security and defence sector. It should be noted that the HEIs faculty members' professional development for the security and defence sector is considered in the article as a continuous process of learning and expanding and improving the general and professional competencies of educators, aimed at supporting and improving the efficiency of their professional activities, which continues throughout teaching career. According to a study [10] by the Harvard Business School, the most effective and popular approach to developing the professional competence of employees in many countries is learning at work. Depending on the needs and goals of a particular employee, the development of his professional competence at work can take various forms, from development under the guidance of a mentor to self-development. A single definition of "learning at work" has not been found in the scientific works of scientists or the regulatory and legal documents of Ukraine. The Dictionary of Educational Terms contains the concept of "acquiring education at work", which is formulated as "a way of organising training ... by participating in the performance of job duties and tasks under the guidance of practising specialists involved in the educational process [11, p. 18]. In the Law of Ukraine "On Professional Development of Employees" and other legal documents, learning at work is defined as informal professional development of employees' competencies [12] and individual training. The faculty staff professional development at this stage is most effectively organised based on a synergistic approach, which in educational management is based on the following provisions:

– self-organisation self-development of the faculty staff professional competence in the system of military special pedagogy is based on the laws of synergy;

– the integrity and non-linearity of the faculty staff's professional competence development processes are essential for their effective functioning.

Approaches to the faculty staff professional competence development for HEIs of the security and defence sector are consistent with the views of Ukrainian researcher of educational management H. Yelnikova believes that a synergistic approach in educational management involves “not direct managerial influence on the faculty staff, but the initiation of potential opportunities of teachers, their creative self-expression; creation of a favourable educational environment that is constantly developing and updated” [13].

The main defining feature of the deepening stage of the faculty staff professional competence development for HEIs of the security and defence sector is increasing their attention to research and scientific activities. “In modern practice, writing a dissertation is necessary for everyone who wants to build a career in higher education”, L. Lobanova notes [14]. In order to develop professional competence at this stage, the faculty members must undergo institutional selection and demonstrate readiness to solve complex problems in the field of professional and/or research and innovation activities, which involves a profound rethinking of the existing and creation of new holistic knowledge and/or professional practice.

It should be emphasised that in the conditions of reforming higher military education, the role of a faculty member as a leader of changes also changes significantly. According to this, a modern leader is a person who enjoys authority and respect due to the ability to quickly respond to changes and make the right management decisions that ensure the success of the educational process and the quality of education. This interpretation of leadership comes from its understanding as a set of professional characteristics and the teacher's ability to effectively carry out educational activities.

Conclusions

New requirements for the training of professionals for the security and defence sector of Ukraine create prerequisites for revising the approaches to the faculty staff professional competence development of HEIs and the formation of a new management system for this process.

Modern military education needs faculty staff that possess new technologies, new pedagogical thinking, and methods that are able to ensure the quality of education at the level of European and international educational standards and military professional standards of NATO. Therefore, providing conditions for the effective self-realisation of faculty members, their professional growth and self-development is one of the most critical areas of activity in managing higher military education. It is expedient to organise the development of professional competence of the higher educational institutions of the security and defence sector on the principles of a synergistic approach, creating favourable conditions for the gradual (but not linear) professional development of educators and ensuring favourable communication between all participants. A synergistic approach to the faculty staff's professional competence development is aimed at managing this process as a holistic, dynamic, open system. This approach ensures the maximum emphasis on the professionalism of the faculty staff, encouraging them to self-realise professional self-actualisation, which becomes an essential factor in effective personnel policy in higher education institutions of the security and defence sector.

Prospects for further research consist in the experimental verification of the effectiveness of the proposed management tools for the faculty staff professional competence development in the context of their implementation in the higher education institutions of the security and defence sector in the conditions of adaptation of higher military education to the requirements of NATO standards.

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